

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF IDIOMS WITH TOPONYMIC COMPONENTS IN ENGLISH

*M. Balyasnikova*¹, *F. Saitmuratov*²

Abstract:

The article is dedicated to the linguistic analysis of idiomatic expressions with toponymic components in the English language. Understanding the linguistic features of toponymic idioms provides insights into the cultural and historical spheres of a language.

Key words: onomastic component, toponymic component, phraseological unit, idiom, names, toponyms, linguocultural

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/nvit4w59>

An investigation of phraseological units is one of the urgent problems of modern linguistics. Since phraseology as a science emerged only in the early twentieth century, today there is still a lot of unresolved issues in this area. In particular, explorations of native and foreign scholars dedicated to onomastic phraseology (K. Betehtina, A. Kravchuk, N. Lalayan, G. Manushkina, V. Mokienko, O. Moroz, O. Safronov, and L. Stepanova), first of all give a general description of the material or cover some aspects based on a particular language [1, 122- 135; 2, 15-28]. Its formation is inextricably linked with the names of such prominent linguists as V.V. Vinogradov, N.N. Amosova, A.V. Kunin, I.I. Chernysheva, B.L. Arkhangelsky, V.P. Zhukov, M.T. Tagiyev and others [7, 55-78]. These scientists have made a great contribution to the development of phraseological problems by putting ahead their original research method and paving the way for further research in this area.

Unfortunately, still there are no generally accepted theoretical approaches for dealing with such controversial issues as the nature of onomastic component in phraseological unit and its role in the motivation of idiomatic meaning, semantic status of proper names. Phraseological units (hereinafter referred to as phraseological units) are stable phrases characterized by staying constant in the lexical composition and complicated semantics. The value of phraseological units is not divided into elements corresponding to the elements of its external form, and usually does not follow from the addition of the values of individual elements of phraseological units. An unambiguous understanding of such phraseological units and the interpretation of their meaning are impossible without analyzing the broad context that defines the situation, and, above all, knowledge of the semantic features and characteristics of these units, which are combined in different ways.

¹ *Balyasnikova Marina Aleksandrovna, Senior Teacher of the Department of English Lexicology and Stylistics, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, Uzbekistan*

² *Saitmuratov Fariddun Farxod o'g'li, Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, Uzbekistan*

The modern use of phraseological units with vertical context, characterized by the expansion of their use in various styles of speech.

The clearly pronounced metaphoric nature and the obvious logical inconsistency between the nominative values of the components of phraseological units create the impression of a game, a joke, a pun and disturbs the neutrality of speech.

We absolutely agree with G.P. Manushkina, who argues that the development of a general theory of phraseology cannot be carried out without careful study of the factual material of various languages, because a concept based only on deductive conclusions without reliance on the data of a specific analysis can hardly claim scientific credibility [1, 65-67].

The article discusses toponyms used in phraseology. In the field of phraseology, different terms are used by different researchers to refer to a string of two or more words functioning as a whole and a single term may be used in reference to different phenomena. A proper noun is a noun denoting a particular person, a tame animal, country, town, star, planet, or thing and is normally not preceded by an article or other limiting modifier. In English, proper nouns are spelt with a capital letter. A proper noun, which is a single word, should be distinguished from a proper name, which may or may not consist of more than one word. Like other grammatical categories, the class of proper nouns has unclear boundaries. For example, a number of common nouns with unique denotation are close to proper nouns and are sometimes spelt with a capital letter (e.g., Fate, Nature). On the other hand, a proper name can take on a metaphorical meaning and become a common noun: e.g., eponyms originating from a person's name (boycott > from the Irish landlord Captain Charles).

Analyzing the idioms with toponymic component we have found that all the place names mentioned in idioms are real. In spite of that some of them were mentioned in the Bible, for example, Road to Damascus - if someone has a great and sudden change in their ideas or beliefs, then this is a road to Damascus change, after the conversion of Saint Paul to Christianity while heading to Damascus to persecute Christians, place Damascus is real. The most common place name used in idioms is Rome. For example:

- All roads lead to Rome - This means that there can be many different ways of doing something.

- Fiddle while Rome burns - used when you disapprove because someone is spending too much time or attention on unimportant matters instead of trying to solve bigger and more important problems.

- Rome was not built in a day - this idiom means that many things cannot be done instantly, and require time and patience.

- Big Easy - (USA) The Big Easy is New Orleans, Louisiana.

- Coals to Newcastle - (UK) Taking, bringing, or carrying coals to Newcastle is doing something that is completely unnecessary.

- Crossing the Rubicon - When you are crossing the Rubicon, you are passing a point of no return. After you do this thing, there is no way of turning around. The only way left is forward.

- Dunkirk spirit - (UK) Dunkirk spirit is when people pull together to get through a very difficult time.

- Fiddle while Rome burns - used when you disapprove because someone is spending too much time or attention on unimportant matters instead of trying to solve bigger and more important problems.

- From Missouri - (USA) If someone is from Missouri, then they require clear proof before they will believe something.

- Himalayan blunder - a Himalayan blunder is a very serious mistake or error.

- Lie back and think of England - a humorous expression used when someone has sex without wanting it or enjoying it, and often used when someone has to do another activity or job that they do not want to.

This article provided and analysed many examples of phraseological units with toponymic component and explained their linguocultural features using the descriptive method. Phraseological fund is not just language, but also a cultural and historical heritage of each nation.

References:

- [1]. Antrushina G.B., Afanasyeva O.V., Morozova N.N. *English Lexicology*. - M., 2001. - 288 p.
- [2]. Arnold I.V. *The English Word*. - L., 1986. - 302 p.
- [3]. *Concise Oxford Dictionary. / Eleventh Edition. / Edited by Catherine Soanes, Angus Stevenson*. - Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004. - 1728 p.
- [4]. Courtney R. *Longman Dictionary of Phrasal Verbs*. - M.: Russkiy yazyk Publishers, 1986. - 737p.
- [5]. Ginsburg R.S. and others. *A Course in Modern English Lexicology*. M., 1979. - 269 p.
- [6]. *Longman Dictionary of English Idioms*. - Harlow, L.: Longman, 1979. - 412 p.
- [7]. Rayevskaya N.M. *English Lexicology*. - K., 1979. - 302 p.
- [8]. *Readings in Modern English Lexicology*. - L., 1970. - 239p.
- [9]. *Webster's Third New International Dictionary*. - N.Y.: Merriam - Webster, 2002. - 2783 p.
- [10]. Балясникова М. Прозвища как источник фамилий в английской ономастике // *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit*. - 2024. - С. 375-378.
- [11]. Балясникова М. А. Имена лица с коннотативными компонентами в современном английском языке // *Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*. - 2024. - Т. 7. - №. 3. - С. 308-313.
- [12]. Кунин А.В. *Англо-русский фразеологический словарь: 4-е изд., перераб. и доп.* - М.: Рус. яз., 1984. - 944с.